

Role of MSCT in lung cancer staging

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Relevance.

Lung cancer is now the leading cause of cancer morbidity in the world's population. Men are 7-10 times more likely to develop lung cancer than women. The incidence of the disease increases in proportion to age. Men in their 60s and 69s have a 60 times higher incidence rate than men in their 30s and 39s.

The health and clinical signs associated with lung cancer are highly variable, depending on the stage of tumour growth. The most typical is a prolonged absence of any warning, distressing sensations during the initial period of the disease, which is fully consistent with the concept of prolonged, multi-year tumour growth. The diagnosis of lung cancer has been a difficult and unresolved problem until recently. An analysis of the ratio of patients diagnosed for the first time to those referred for treatment in their staging shows that there has been some stabilisation in the last few decades, with an overall unfavourable situation.

The long absence of clinical manifestations in the early (I-II) stages of the disease required the development of a set of diagnostic measures for large populations in the form of large-scale, systematic follow-up examinations. The leading place here takes the performance of review roentgenograms, and when indicated - computed tomography. The timely performance of MSCT allows the majority of patients to make an accurate diagnosis, determine the stage of disease development and choose the optimal treatment tactics.

Purpose of the study:

- Evaluate the role of MSCT in determining the stage of lung cancer.

Research objectives:

- Describe the signs of change in lung tissue at different stages of lung cancer.
- Determine the role of MSCT in determining the stage of disease.

Materials and methods.

Forty-eight patients with lung cancer were examined. Materials were collected from the archives of the Republican Specialised Scientific-Practical Medical Centre for Oncology and Radiology for the period 2020-2022.

The results of clinical, laboratory and radiological investigations in 48 patients admitted to hospital with lung cancer were analysed.

The patients were allocated according to gender and age, the results of which are presented in Table 1.

Age	Men		Women	
	n	%	n	%
31-40	2	4,2	1	2,1
41-50	6	12,5	2	4,2
51-60	10	20,8	3	6,3
Older than 60	20	41,6	4	8,3
Average age	59,52		54,7	
Total	38	79,1	10	20,9

The patients were also divided according to histological verification. (Figure 1):

From this chart, it can be observed that adenocarcinoma of varying degrees of verification (46%) accounts for the majority of the histological type. The next types in terms of distribution are small cell carcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma 31%; 21% respectively.

The patients were also classified according to clinical and anatomical staging. (Figure 2):

Research results

The 48 patients were predominantly male - 38 (79.1%), 10 female (20.9%); age ranged from 38 to 81 years. The average age of the patients was 59.6 years. Most patients of both sexes were between 47 and 69 years of age - 32 patients (66.7%). Majority of the patients studied were males, with age between 51 and 81 years - 30 patients (62,5%), middle-aged, elderly and senile. These data show that the disease is also a social problem. Of 48 patients, 14 had the central form and 26 had the peripheral form.

The use of MSCT scans, gave the most accurate picture and information in determining the stage of lung cancer and this, in turn, allowed the treating physician to carry out the best possible treatment.

Conclusion

The study examined the diagnostic features of MSCT staging of lung cancer. The need for timely use of MSCT in patients with suspected lung cancer has been demonstrated.

MSCT in lung cancer is an essential examination method. As it not only allows the tumour to be detected at an early stage, but also allows the progression of treatment to be assessed.

References: N. Hollings, P. Shaw. Diagnostic imaging of lung cancer. European Respiratory Journal.

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